

Carbon Nanofibers with Multi-Channeled Silicon Compartments: Fabrication and Electrochemical Properties

H. Yang¹, B.-S. Lee¹, W.-R. Yu^{1,*}

¹ Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Seoul National University, Seoul, Korea

* Corresponding author (woongryu@snu.ac.kr)

Keywords: *Carbon nanofibers, Multi-channel, Silicon compartments, Co-axial electrospinning, Electrochemical performance*

1 Introduction

Since the early 1990s, lithium-ion batteries (LIB) have been widely used as power sources mainly for small portable electronic devices. Higher specific capacity and longer cycling performance are two main elements driving intensive research toward the development of advanced LIBs [1].

Due to the high discharge capacity of 4200mAhg⁻¹ and relatively low working potential (about 0.5V vs Li/Li⁺) of silicon (Si) [2], silicon has been regarded as a strong candidate for advanced anode materials that can replace the current graphite anodes with low specific capacity of 372mAhg⁻¹ [3]. Si anodes, however, have shown serious problems such as large volume change (up to about 400%), pulverization, and electrical contact loss during charging (lithiation) and discharging (delithiation) processes. In order to overcome disadvantages of above problems, many researches have been carried out to understand lithiation phenomena of Si [4, 5, 6], concluding that crystalline Si goes through anisotropic volume expansion with amorphization during lithiation. The composition methods of Si and carbon (C) for LIB anodes have been researched since 2000s, including vapor grown [7, 8] and etching silicon catalytically [9]. However, these methods are not proper for mass production. Based on electrospinning, which has relatively advantages in the mass production, we have studied 'compartmentalized Si within carbon matrix, e.g., Si core/ C shell nanofibers [10], demonstrating better specific capacity than carbon-based anodes and showing stable charge and discharge cycles due to the buffering effect of carbon shell, i.e., accommodation of large volume change of Si. As this study is one of continuing research, it aims to fabricate nanofibers with 'multi-channeled Si compartments within C matrix'.

In this work, carbon nanofibers (CNF) with multi-channeled Si compartments were fabricated for higher buffering effect of carbon matrix and more electric contacts between Si and carbon. Using material compositions that were found in our previous work [11] to be highly suitable for stable coaxial electrospinning, firstly bi-component (styrene-co-acrylonitrile (SAN)/Si and poly (acrylonitrile) (PAN)) precursor nanofibers were electrospun in multi-islands-in-sea type. Through a subsequent thermal treatment, the islands were then burnt out, leaving multi-channeled carbon nanofibers with stuffed Si nanoparticles. Finally, the electrochemical performance of the developed carbon nanofibers with multi-channeled Si compartments was characterized using coin-cell type battery.

2 Experimental

2.1 Preparation of bi-component nanofibers in Islands-in-sea type

PAN (Mw=200,000g mol⁻¹, Misui chemical) and SAN (AN 28.5mol%, Mw=120,000g mol⁻¹, Cheil industries) were dissolved in *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF, purity 99.5%, Daejung chemical) respectively. Their concentrations were controlled to be 20 and 30 wt.%, respectively. Those solutions were then ultrasonicated for 5h and further stirred at 90°C for 12h. Si nanoparticles (1g, D<100nm, Aldrich) were added into the SAN solution (10g), which was further stirred at 90°C for 24h. PAN and Si nanoparticle added SAN solutions were used as the shell and core materials, respectively, in the coaxial electrospinning.

Two kinds of multi-channeled nanofibers (two- and four-channeled compartments) were electrospun using specially designed nozzles. The diameters of

the core and outer nozzle tips were 1mm and 0.7mm respectively. The co-axial electrospinning conditions were set up as follows: applied voltage – 18kV, tip-to-collector distance (TCD) – 15cm, and the flow rates of the core and shell solutions – 0.5 and 1.5~1.75ml h⁻¹ respectively. A schematic diagram for electrospun nanofibers with two-channeled Si compartments is provided in Fig.1. For other channel case, the same nozzle system was also applied except the core nozzle.

2.2 Thermal treatment

Precursor nanofibers were thermally treated for their stabilization and carbonization. The stabilization step was carried out at 270~300°C under air atmosphere, during which the removal of hydrogen in PAN started, transforming PAN into ladder structured PAN. The carbonization step was carried out at 1000°C under nitrogen atmosphere, increasing carbon purity in shell and removing core material (SAN). The increasing rates of temperature were 0.5°C min⁻¹ and 10°C min⁻¹ for the stabilization step and carbonization, respectively (see Fig.2 for detailed procedure [11]).

2.3 Microstructural characterization

The morphology of the carbon nanofibers with Si compartments was analyzed using a field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM). Their inner structures were also analyzed using a high-resolution transmission electron microscope (HR-TEM). Wide angle X-ray diffraction (WAXD) was used to characterize the carbon nanofibers.

2.4 Electrochemical characterization

A two-electrode 2032-type coin capsule was employed to assess the electrochemical performances of the carbon nanofibers with multi-channeled Si compartments. The anode slurry was prepared by mixing the carbon nanofibers with multi-channeled Si compartments (60wt%), acetylene black (20wt%, Alfa Aesar), and poly(vinylidene fluoride) (20wt%, Alfa Aesar) in 1-methyl-2pyrrolidinone (Alfa Aesar). The mixture (slurry) was screen-printed on a copper foil (Alfa Aesar) and dried. A lithium foil (Alfa Aesar) was used as the counter and reference electrode for a half-cell configuration and glass fibers (Whatman) were used as the separator. 1 M LiPF₆ in a mixed solution of propylene carbonate and diethyl

carbonate (volume ratio 1:1, TSC Michigan) was used as the electrolyte. The coin-cells were assembled according to the following order: anode (slurry printed on copper foil), electrolyte, separator, and cathode (lithium foil) and then crimped and closed in Ar-filled glove box. The electrochemical performance was then measured at a current densities of 50 mA g⁻¹ for lithiation and delithiation between 0.01 and 1.5 V.

3 Results and discussion

Two- and four- channeled carbon nanofibers were fabricated using co-axial electrospinning. Firstly, the feasibility of coaxial electrospinning for manufacturing the multi-channeled carbon nanofibers was investigated by fabricating carbon nanofibers with void channels, i.e., without Si nanoparticles. The morphologies of such carbon nanofibers were examined by SEM and TEM. The microscopic images of the carbon nanofibers in Fig. 3 clearly demonstrate that uniform and hollowed carbon nanofibers with two void channels were manufactured. The compartments and the wall were continuously formed within the carbon nanofibers. Carbon nanofibers with four void channels were also examined by SEM and TEM as shown in Fig. 4. As the two channel case, four compartments and the wall were uniformly and continuously formed within Fig.4. Note that in Fig. 4 (b), three compartments were viewed, the other being covered by the middle one. It was concluded that the coaxial electrospinning process is suitable for fabricating the carbon nanofibers with multi-channeled compartments.

Si nanoparticles were added to multi-channeled compartments in the carbon nanofibers during the electrospinning. As shown in Figs.5 and 6, continuous carbon nanofibers with two- and four-channeled Si compartments were successfully manufactured in the multi-channeled compartments core/shell structure. The diameter of the carbon nanofibers with multi-channeled Si compartments was larger than that of hollowed carbon nanofibers by 200-300nm. In Figs.5 (c) and 6 (c), the carbon nanofibers with multi-channeled compartments show beads-on-string shape, which was caused by the aggregation of Si nanoparticles. Fig.6 (c) shows Si nanoparticles filled in all compartments, even in the middle compartment, whereas the carbon

nanofibers with two-channeled compartments showed Si-free middle compartments as shown in Fig.5 (c). Fig.5 (d) shows the HR-TEM image of Si nanoparticle and carbon shell in the carbon nanofibers with four-channeled compartments. Periodic lattices of crystalline Si nanoparticles, turbostratic structure of carbon shell, and the boundary between Si nanoparticle and carbon shell can be clearly observed.

Fig.7 shows WAXD curve of the carbon nanofibers with two- and four-channeled Si compartments. Note that the black and red lines show WAXD curve of the carbon nanofibers with two- and four-channeled Si compartments, respectively. The two curves are almost the same, showing two broad peaks for turbostratic carbon and seven sharp peaks for crystalline Si: (002), (101), (111), (220), (311), (400), (331), (422), and (511) respectively. This confirms that crystalline Si still remained even after the thermal treatment without any chemical reactions like SiO₂ and SiC involved. The PAN shell was changed into turbostratic structure having slightly mismatched layer-sequence. Overall, it is concluded that the carbon nanofibers with multi-channeled Si compartments have been successfully fabricated using coaxial electrospinning process.

4 Summary

The carbon nanofibers with multi-channeled compartments and Si compartments were successfully fabricated using coaxial electrospinning and subsequent thermal treatment. The Si compartments inside the carbon nanofibers was clearly demonstrated via SEM and TEM analyses. It was confirmed that there were no additional chemical reactions between Si and the carbon during the carbonization process. The electrochemical performance of the carbon nanofibers with multi-channeled Si compartments is being investigated for LIB anodes and will be presented at the Conference.

References

- [1] T. Song, J. Xia, J.-H. Lee, D.H. Lee, M.-S. Kwon, J.-M. Choi, J. Wu, S.K. Doo, H. Chang, W.I. Park, D.S. Zang, H. Kim, Y. Huang, K.-C. Hwang, J.A. Rogers, U. Paik, "Arrays of Sealed Silicon Nanotubes As Anodes for Lithium Ion Batteries", *Nano Letters*, Vol. 10, pp 1710-1716, 2010.
- [2] C.K. Chan, R. Ruffo, S.S. Hong, R.A. Huggins, Y. Cui, "Structural and electrochemical study of the reaction of lithium with silicon nanowires", *Journal of Power Sources*, Vol. 189, pp 34-39, 2009.
- [3] S.-B. Son, J.E. Trevey, H. Roh, S.-H. Kim, K.-B. Kim, J.S. Cho, J.-T. Moon, C.M. DeLuca, K.K. Maute, M.L. Dunn, H.N. Han, K.H. Oh, S.-H. Lee, "Microstructure Study of Electrochemically Driven Li_xSi", *Advanced Energy Materials*, Vol. 1, pp 1199-1204, 2011.
- [4] X.H. Liu, H. Zheng, L. Zhong, S. Huang, K. Karki, L.Q. Zhang, Y. Liu, A. Kushima, W.T. Liang, J.W. Wang, J.-H. Cho, E. Epstein, S.A. Dayeh, S.T. Picraux, T. Zhu, J. Li, J.P. Sullivan, J. Cumings, C. Wang, S.X. Mao, Z.Z. Ye, S. Zhang, J.Y. Huang, "Anisotropic Swelling and Fracture of Silicon Nanowires during Lithiation", *Nano Letters*, Vol.11, pp 3312-3318, 2011
- [5] X.H. Liu, L.Q. Zhang, L. Zhong, Y. Liu, H. Zheng, J.W. Wang, J.-H. Cho, S.A. Dayeh, S.T. Picraux, J.P. Sullivan, S.X. Mao, Z.Z. Ye, J.Y. Huang, "Ultrafast Electrochemical Lithiation of Individual Si nanowire Anodes", *Nano Letters*, Vol.11, pp 2251-2258, 2011
- [6] S.W. Lee, M.T. McDowell, J.W. Choi, Y. Cui, "Anomalous Shape Changes of Silicon Nanopillars by Electrochemical Lithiation" *Nano Letters*, Vol.11, pp 3034-3039, 2011
- [7] L.-F. Cui, Y. Yang, C.-M. Hsu, Y. Cui, "Carbon-Silicon Core-Shell Nanowires as High Capacity Electrode for Lithium Ion Batteries", *Nano Letters*, Vol. 9, pp 3370-3374, 2009.
- [8] M. Yoshio, H. Wang, K. Fujuda, T. Umeno, N. Dimov, Z. Ogumni, "Carbon-Coated Si as a Lithium-Ion Battery Anode Material", *Journal of The Electrochemical Society*, Vol. 149, pp A1598-A1603, 2002.
- [9] R. Huang, X. Fan, W. shen, J. zhu, "Carbon-coated silicon nanowire array films for high-performance lithium-ion battery anodes", *Applied Physics Letters*, Vol. 95, 133119, 2009
- [10] B. Lee, S. Son, K. Park, J. Seo, S. Lee, I. Choi, K. Oh, W. Yu, "Fabrication of Si core/C shell nanofibers and their electrochemical performances as a lithium-ion battery anode", *Journal of Power Sources*, Vol. 206, pp 267-273, 2012.
- [11] B. Lee, K. Park, W. Yu, J. Youk, "An effective Method for Manufacturing Hollow Carbon Nanofibers and Microstructural Analysis", *Macromolecular Research*, Vol. 20, pp 605-613, 2012.

Fig.1. Schematic diagram illustrating the coaxial electrospinning for fabricating carbon nanofibers with two-channelled Si compartments and structural changes during thermal treatment

Fig.2. Continuous thermal treatment of the precursor nanofibers[3]

(a)

(b)

Fig.3. (a) SEM and (b) TEM images of the carbon nanofibers with two void channels

(b)

(c)

Fig.4. (a) SEM and (b) TEM images of the carbon nanofibers with four void channels

Fig.5. SEM images at (a) low and (b) high magnifications and TEM image (c) of carbon nanofibers with two-channelled Si compartments

(d)

Fig.6. SEM images at (a) low and (b) high magnifications, (c) TEM and (d) HR-TEM images of the carbon nanofibers with four-channeled Si compartments

Fig.7. WAXD pattern of carbon nanofibers two-, and four-channeled Si compartments